

Influence of Embedded Optical Fibers on Tensile Strength and Interlaminar Shear Strength of Composite Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The optical fibers were embedded between central laminates of the specimen, and influences of embedded optical fibers on tensile strength and interlaminar shear strength were investigated. In tensile test, there was no noticeable deterioration on the tensile properties in $[0^\circ]_4$ and $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ laminates. In $[90^\circ]_4$ laminates, the tensile strength increased up to 20%. In the interlaminar shear test, when the optical fibers were embedded perpendicular to the reinforced direction, the interlaminar shear strength was decreased slightly. The position of fracture surface was shifted due to the embedded optical fibers. The relation between embedded optical fibers and stress distribution was discussed using finite element analysis.

Keywords: Composite laminates, Optical fiber, Tensile properties, Interlaminar shear strength

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites are expected as advanced materials for future aircraft and space structures. Because of their particular damage modes, such as matrix crackings and delaminations, it is desirable to establish non-destructive evaluation techniques. One promising approach to establish new non-destructive evaluation techniques is the concept of smart structures.⁽¹⁾ A fiber optic sensor is one of the most effective sensors for this concept; fiber optic sensors will be embedded into composite laminates, and used as nerves for structures. Embedded fiber optic sensors are expected to have considerable potential for in-service monitoring to detect damages, and eliminate periodic inspection by conventional non-destructive means. Furthermore, they provide effective ways to investigate the fracture mechanism of composite laminates on a micromechanical scale. The authors tested two types of embedded fiber optic sensors (embedded fiber optic strain gage and embedded crack sensor using optical fiber breaks), and showed that the embedded fiber optic sensors were effective for the investigation of the fracture mechanism of composite laminates.⁽²⁾ To measure strains accurately and to detect crackings certainly using optical fibers, optical fibers had to be uncoated before embedding.

To improve the technique for detection of the damage using embedded fiber

optic sensors, it is necessary to investigate the influence of embedded optical fibers on the mechanical properties of composite laminates. However, there is still much left to be studied hereafter about that. Influence of embedded optical fibers along the sensing area (optical fibers are uncoated) should be investigated in detail.

In the present study, tensile strength and interlaminar shear strength of the specimens with embedded optical fibers were measured. In the interlaminar shear test, relation between embedded optical fibers and stress distribution was discussed using finite element analysis. The specimen was made of graphite-epoxy prepreg plies (TORAY T300/#2500) and single mode optical fibers (3M FN-SN-3221, 125 μ m in uncoated diameter). The optical fibers were uncoated and embedded between central laminates of the specimen.

2. INFLUENCE OF EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBERS ON TENSILE PROPERTIES

2.1. Tensile test with various lay-up sequences of the specimens

2.1.1. Specimen

The specimens were made of 4 plies of graphite-epoxy prepreg, and lay-up sequences were $[0^{\circ}]_4$, $[45^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}]_s$ and $[90^{\circ}]_4$. Specimen designations were described in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the arrangements of prepreg plies and optical fibers in the embedding process. One to five optical fibers were put between central laminates of each specimens in the same interval. The size of the specimen was 200x25x1mm. Cross sectional views of the specimens were showed in Figure 2. When the direction of embedded optical fiber was not parallel to the reinforced direction, embedded optical fibers were surrounded by a resin-rich region. As the angle between reinforcing fibers and embedded optical fibers increase, the lengths of the resin-rich region increased. The maximum length of the resin-rich region was about 1.5mm, and the resin-rich regions were not connected to the neighboring resin-rich regions even in the specimens with the shortest intervals of embedded optical fibers.

2.1.2. Results and discussions

Table 2 shows the average of elastic modulus and tensile strength of five specimens. Elastic modulus and tensile strengths normalized with respect to the average of control specimens (specimen type: A0, B0, C0) were presented in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 shows that the elastic modulus of the specimens was not affected by embedded optical fibers. In the case of tensile strength, there were no degradation for all types of the specimens. However, in $[90^{\circ}]_4$ laminates, tensile strengths were increased about 20% preferably. And the increase in tensile strength was scarcely dependent of the number of embedded optical fibers. It seems that embedded optical fibers have the reinforcing effect for 90 degree laminate. However, elastic modulus was not affected by embedding the optical fibers, and the increases of tensile strengths was independent of the number of embedded optical fibers. Furthermore, the area ratio of the embedded optical fibers to the cross section of specimen were very small (up to 0.25%). So, it is not enough to discuss the reinforcing effect of embedded optical fibers on the micromechanical scale.

2.2. Tensile test with various thickness of the specimens

2.2.1. Specimen

To obtain the thickness of which tensile strength was not affected by embedded optical fibers, tensile test with various thickness of the specimens were conducted. The specimens were made of 4, 6, 8 and 10 plies of graphite-epoxy prepreg, and three optical fibers were embedded in each specimens perpendicular to the reinforced direction. The lay-up sequences were $[90^{\circ}]_n$ (n=4, 6, 8 and 10). Table 3 shows designation and thickness of the specimens.

The size of the specimen was 200x25mm, and the thicknesses were about 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5. The specimen type C3-1 corresponds to the type C3 in the section 2.1. Strength measurements were carried out on five specimens for each type of the specimen.

2.2.2. Results and discussions

Figure 5 shows measured tensile strengths normalized with respect to the average of the specimens with no embedded optical fibers. The tensile strengths of 1mm thickness specimens with embedded optical fibers were 20% higher than that of the specimens without embedded optical fibers. As the thickness of the specimens increased, the difference of the tensile strengths between the specimens with optical fibers and with no optical fibers was decreased. In the case of the specimens with thickness above 2.0mm (sixteen times as long as the diameter of embedded optical fiber), tensile strength was scarcely affected by the embedded optical fibers. When the optical fibers were embedded perpendicular to the reinforced direction, a care should be taken about the influence of embedded optical fibers in the case that the thickness of composite laminates is below 2.0mm.

3. INFLUENCE OF EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBERS ON INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH

Interlaminar shear strength is one of the most critical properties in laminated composites. It depends on the properties of interfaces between reinforced fibers and matrix resin. When optical fibers are embedded between laminates, new interfaces between optical fibers and matrix resin come into existence. However, degradations on interlaminar shear strength with embedded optical fibers have never been studied enough. In this section, influence of embedded optical fibers on interlaminar shear strength were discussed by interlaminar shear test and finite element analysis.

3.1. Interlaminar shear test

3.1.1. Specimen

The specimens were made of 8 plies of graphite-epoxy prepreg ($[0^\circ]_8$). Optical fibers were uncoated and embedded between central laminates of the specimens. The geometries of the specimens were detailed in Figure 6. The size of the specimen was 16x10x2mm. In the specimen type A1 and A7, optical fibers were embedded parallel to the reinforced direction. Seven optical fibers were embedded into the specimens of type A7 with the space of 1mm. In the specimen type B1, B2 and B3, optical fibers were embedded perpendicular to the reinforced direction, and the distances between embedded optical fibers were different (B1:2mm, B2:6mm, B3:8mm). Control specimens without optical fibers (type A0) were also tested.

3.1.2. Results and discussions

Interlaminar shear strength was measured by short beam three point bending method at a span to depth ratio of 5:1. Table 4 shows the average of shear strength of six specimens. Figure 7 shows measured shear strength normalized with respect to the average of control specimen (A0). In the specimen of types A1 and A7, there was no noticeable deterioration on interlaminar shear strength. In the specimen of type B3, shear strengths were decreased slightly; the average of shear strength in specimen of type B3 was decreased about 6% compared to the control specimen. The side views of the tested specimens were showed in Figure 8. The positions of fracture surfaces in specimens of type A0, A1, A7 and B1 were in a center of the specimen. In the specimen of type B2 and B3, the position of fracture surface was shifted to upper and lower part around the optical fiber. These results show that as the distance between loading point and optical fiber increases, interlaminar shear strengths were decreased slightly, and the position of fracture surface was

shifted due to the embedded optical fibers. To discuss the shift of fracture surface, stress distributions were analyzed using finite element analysis in the next section.

3.2. Finite element analysis

3.2.1. Finite element model

Two models were created and stress distributions were analyzed; one was for the specimen without optical fibers, the other was for the specimen with embedded optical fibers. Because of the symmetry of loading condition in both models, only one-half the specimen length was considered as shown in Figure 9. In the case of specimen with embedded optical fibers, the model of optical fiber and resin-rich region (Figure 10) was integrated to the model shown in Figure 9. The length of the resin-rich region was chosen to 0.875mm (seven times as long as the diameter of embedded optical fibers). Material properties used in the analysis were: $E_x=127\text{GPa}$, $E_y=8.8\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.34$, $G_{xy}=4.4\text{GPa}$ for composite laminates ; $E=73\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.23$ for optical fiber; $E=3.3\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.3$ for resin-rich region. The loading condition was assumed to be the cosine distribution as shown in Figure 9.

3.2.2. Results and discussions

Figures 11 and 12 show the distributions of shear stress normalized with respect to the maximum shear stress based on the elementary beam theory. ($\bar{\tau}_{xy}$) The transverse axis (y) was normalized with respect to the thickness of the specimen (h). In the case of the specimen without optical fibers, shear stress showed maximum value around the upper area near the loading point. Except for the position $x=3.0$, shear stress distributions were almost same in both types of the specimen. However, at the position of the specimen where optical fiber was embedded ($x=3.0$), two peaks can be seen in composite area (denoted as ① and ② in Figure 12). These results show that the embedded optical fibers change the stress distributions around the optical fibers, and may cause the shift of fracture surface as shown in the section 3.1.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Tensile strength and interlaminar shear strength of the specimens with embedded optical fibers were measured, and stress distributions in the interlaminar shear test were analyzed using finite element analysis.

- (1)Tensile test : There was no noticeable deterioration on the tensile properties in $[0^\circ]_4$ and $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ laminates. In $[90^\circ]_4$ laminates, tensile strengths were increased about 20%. In the case of the specimens with thickness above 2.0mm, tensile strength was scarcely affected by the embedded optical fibers.
- (2)Interlaminar shear test : As the distance between the loading point and the optical fiber increases, interlaminar shear strengths were decreased slightly, and the position of fracture surface was shifted due to the embedded optical fibers.
- (3)Finite element analysis for interlaminar shear test : The embedded optical fibers change the stress distributions around the optical fibers.

References

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Table 1. Specimen description for the tensile test.

Specimen type	A0	A1	A3	A5	B0	B1	B3	B5	C0	C1	C3	C5
Lay-up sequence	$[0^\circ]_4$				$[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_S$				$[90^\circ]_4$			
Number of optical fibers	0	1	3	5	0	1	3	5	0	1	3	5

Figure 1. Embedding optical fibers in composite laminates.

Figure 2. Cross sectional view of the specimen.

Table 2. Results of the tensile test.

Specimen type	A0	A1	A3	A5	B0	B1	B3	B5	C0	C1	C3	C5
Elastic modulus (GPa)	117	122	120	110	14.7	14.9	14.5	14.8	8.0	8.0	8.4	8.3
Tensile strength (MPa)	1590	1470	1610	1580	167	172	167	166	57	66	69	66

Figure 3. Normalized elastic modulus.

Figure 4. Normalized tensile strength.

Table 3. Specimen description for the tensile test with various thicknesses of the specimens.

Specimen type	C3-1	C3-2	C3-3	C3-4
Lay-up sequence	$[90^\circ]_4$	$[90^\circ]_6$	$[90^\circ]_8$	$[90^\circ]_{10}$
Thickness (mm)	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5

Figure 5. Normalized tensile strength with various thicknesses of the specimens.

Figure 6. Interlaminar shear test specimens.

Figure 7. Normalized interlaminar shear strength.

Table 4. Results of the interlaminar shear test.

Specimen	A0	A1	A7	B1	B2	B3
mean (MPa)	84.4	84.6	86.7	82.8	81.9	79.4
C.V. (%)	1.6	2.1	1.3	2.3	2.2	1.6

Figure 8. Side view of the tested specimens.

Figure 9. Finite element model (without optical fiber).

Figure 10. Finite element model (around optical fiber).

Figure 11. Shear stress distributions (without optical fiber).

Figure 12. Shear stress distributions (with optical fiber).